

PRODUCTION AND EVALUATION OF COCUCYNNE FETTUCCHINE PASTA

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Production and Evaluation of Cocucynne Fettuccine Pasta

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Abstract

This study aimed to produce COCUCYNNE Fettuccine Pasta and analyze its physicochemical contents, acceptability, and marketability level during the school year of 2023- 2024 at Barangay Tumana, Marikina City. Experimental method of research was used, utilizing survey questionnaire as the data gathering instrument which involved 30 pasta lovers, 30 pasta sellers, and 30 pasta makers as respondents. This study also used the 9 - point Hedonic rating scale for the acceptability and 5-point Likert scale for the marketability of the product. The data revealed that Hundred-gram of produced COCUCYNNE Fettuccine Pasta with 50% of taro root, turmeric, and lemongrass powder contain 4.07 milligrams of iron, 65.7 grams of total carbohydrates, a pH level of 6.05, and a moisture content of 14.6 grams. In addition, the three groups of respondents. The pasta lovers, pasta sellers, and pasta makers respondents evaluated the acceptability of the produced COCUCYNNE Fettuccine Pasta with 25%, 50%, and 75% proportions in terms of appearance, aroma, taste, and texture as Very Acceptable Level as evidence by grand weighted means of 8.25, 7.81, and 8.30, respectively. Comments and suggestions were given by the three groups of respondents for further improvement of the product which led to no significant difference on their evaluations. The respondents rated the marketability of product in different proportion proportions of taro root, turmeric, and lemongrass powder as Very High Level as manifested by their overall weighted mean of 4.77, 4.67 and 4.88, respectively resulting to were no significant differences in the evaluations of the groups of respondents on the level of marketability of the product. The respondents suggested that adding cornstarch and baking soda will improve the produced COCUCYNNE Fettuccine Pasta to make its texture more elastic when boiled. They also commented that improving its color will make it more palatable by using natural coloring from dried pigmented plants.

Keywords: *acceptability, marketability, physicochemical analysis, production, evaluation*

Introduction

Pasta is considered one of the comfort foods of most Filipinos. Everyone loves to eat pasta. The popularity of pasta dishes surged in the Philippines and is always present in social events, restaurant menus, and family gatherings and is considered part of every Filipino occasion. There is also a certain tradition that when someone celebrates his/her birthday, they should eat “Pancit” as it symbolizes long life.

It is necessary to understand the reasons behind the Filipinos’ affection for Pasta. Pasta is rich in carbohydrates which is a primary source of energy for the body. For the researcher, she finds it as simple pleasure to enjoy a plate of delicious pasta, because of its unique texture, and chewy and soft consistency of pasta. When combined with sauces and toppings the taste can help activate feelings of comfort. Eating pasta can be a one-way destressing.

According to Int. J. Environ. Res. Public Health (2021), Pasta is a staple food in Mediterranean countries which became very popular all over the world. The nutritional component of Pasta is key in the Mediterranean Diet and its consumption has been positively associated with a low body mass index and prevention of overweight and obesity risk conditions.

In his study, the pasta shall be produced with healthier version which contains taro root, turmeric, and lemon grass extract namely.

One of its ingredients is taro root which according to Fincher (2022), has white meat with purple flecks throughout and brown skin. Its texture and slight sweetness when cooked are similar to potatoes. It offers three times as much fiber as a potato and is also a good source of potassium, vitamin C, and vitamin A. Additionally, it offers a host of possible health advantages, such as better blood sugar control and heart health.

Another ingredient is turmeric, an herb from the ginger family which is also known as “Luyangdilaw” in Filipino. Turmeric has an aromatic strong flavor which has a yellowish orange color. Its appearance has a resemblance of ginger (“7 Spices That Define Filipino Cuisine,” 2020).

According to National Nutrition Council (2021), turmeric is widely popular in the Philippines because of benefits that it can give and help to people. Turmeric is a great spice that has many vitamins and minerals for boosting one’s health by means of using it as spices in other dishes either powdered or chopped.

Another ingredient of the pasta to be produced is lemongrass which is defined by Jurimas n.d. also known as “Tanglad”. It is a type of grass that is widely distributed since it is not difficult to grow. It is most frequently seen in tropical regions, particularly in Asia. Lemon grass has blue-green leaves that turn red in the fall and release a potent lemon scent when they are injured. It is a tufted perennial grass with long, sharp-edged blades and a flavor reminiscent of citrus. These are used to treat digestive tract spasms, stomach aches, high

blood pressure, convulsions, discomfort, vomiting, coughing, achy joints, fever, the common cold, and weariness. Additionally, it functions as a mild astringent and a germicide.

Because of the forecited benefits, the researcher tried to produce fettuccine pasta using taro root, turmeric, and lemongrass powder.

Research Questions

This study aimed to produce and evaluate COCUCYNNE Fettuccine Pasta in Barangay Tumana, Marikina City, during the academic year 2023–2024. Specifically, it sought answers to the following questions:

1. How can COCUCYNNE Fettuccine Pasta be produced using taro root, turmeric, and lemongrass powder as additional ingredients in three different proportions of 25%, 50%, and 75%, respectively?
2. What is the physicochemical analysis of COCUCYNNE Fettuccine Pasta in terms of the following?
 - 2.1. Nutrients (Iron and Carbohydrates)
 - 2.2. Shelf Life (Water Activity and pH Level)
3. What is the level of acceptability of the produced COCUCYNNE Fettuccine Pasta with three different proportions of taro root, turmeric, and lemongrass powder in terms of the following criteria?
 - 3.1. Appearance
 - 3.2. Aroma
 - 3.3. Taste
 - 3.4. Texture
4. Are there significant differences in the evaluations of the three groups of respondents on the level of acceptability of the produced COCUCYNNE Fettuccine Pasta in terms of the cited criteria?
5. What is the level of marketability of the produced COCUCYNNE Fettuccine Pasta in three different proportions of taro root, turmeric, and lemongrass powder in terms of the following criteria?
 - 5.1. Supply Availability
 - 5.2. Consumer Demand
 - 5.3. Production Cost
6. Are there significant differences in the evaluations of the three groups of respondents on the level of marketability on produced COCUCYNNE Fettuccine Pasta in terms of the forecited criteria?
7. What are the comments and suggestions offered by the respondents to improve the produced product?

Literature Review

Taro root is very rich in nutrients which according to Thomas (2022), one serving contains one-third of the daily required manganese intake, which is beneficial for bones, metabolism, and avoiding blood clotting. It also has a lot of vitamins that are helpful for the immunological, circulatory, and skin systems as well as the eyes and skin. Along with these additional health advantages, taro roots also help with digestion, blood sugar regulation, lowering diabetes risk, lowering heart disease risk, preventing cramping, and more.

Choudnary (2023) remarked that taro root is a well-liked due to its distinctive nutty flavor. It is full of healthy nutrients and is utilized in many delicious dishes around the globe. Taro root can help in weight loss, increase energy levels, maintain good health for heart, muscular, and digestive system. Thanks to its vitamins A, B, and C contents and a variety of minerals, it also aids in enhancing immunity, lowering the risk of cancer, and the aging process. Taro root can also effectively treat hypertension. It is both a low glycemic meal and possesses antioxidant qualities. To enjoy the root's various advantages, it should be included in the diet in moderation. Turmeric, is another ingredient of the product of this study. It is a spice that comes from the ginger family, where the major ingredient is curcumin which is responsible for its yellowish color. According to one study, individuals with ulcerative colitis who added 2 grams of curcumin to their daily dose of prescription medication had a better likelihood of keeping their condition under control than those who used the medication alone. Another study found that taking 90 milligrams of curcumin twice daily for 18 months helped persons without dementia perform better in terms of memory. Researchers hypothesized that curcumin's antioxidant capabilities decreased brain inflammation. ("7 Health Benefits of Turmeric," 2021).

The 'superfood' status earned by turmeric as a gold spice is believed to protect cells from inflammation and damage as per Lewin, (2023). Additionally, he stated that turmeric helps lessen arthritis symptoms, halt the aging process, and even stop the proliferation of malignant cells. In addition, it is thought to improve mood, memory, and brain function, and some studies indicate that it may be effective in treating illnesses like stroke and Alzheimer's.

The next ingredient of this study's product is lemongrass. This is one of tropical plants, a native of Southeast Asia. According to Begum (2022), it is a common ingredient in Thai cuisine. It is currently grown throughout North and South America, Australia, and Africa, and it is frequently utilized as a natural cure for high blood pressure, neurological difficulties, and digestive problems. Because lemongrass includes citral, it has a naturally occurring plant chemical with anti-inflammatory qualities. It is also said to have antibacterial and antifungal characteristics in addition to its historical use as a painkiller and fever reducer.

Additionally, according to Sachdev (2020), lemongrass has been used for generations in India. It offers immunity-boosting qualities

that are crucial for developing the body's defense system, particularly during a pandemic. Lemongrass' high potassium content has also been demonstrated, making it the ideal herb for regulating blood pressure. This is due to the fact that potassium levels aid in the production of urine, stimulate blood circulation, which lowers blood pressure, and also cleanses the liver.

An article by Bresciani et al. (2022) stated that pasta is a food that is becoming more and more popular all over the world. Many formulations have been created to enhance its nutritional profile. It is widely acknowledged that semolina with a high protein and gluten content makes the best raw material for making traditional dry pasta. Understanding the correlation between processing factors and pasta quality when various raw materials are utilized is essential for optimizing the redesign of the production process. Pasta plays a key role in the Mediterranean Diet. The World Health Organization (WHO) and Food and Agriculture Organization (FAO) of the United Nations described pasta as a healthy, sustainable, and quality food model.

Methodology

Research Design

The present study used the experimental and descriptive methods of research in order to attain its objectives. This method was used in the production of pasta using powdered taro root, turmeric, and lemongrass as ingredients and in determining the development, physicochemical analysis, acceptability, and marketability of COCUCYNNE Fettuccine pasta with 25%, 50%, and 75% proportion.

Experimental method of research, as stated by Singh (2021), is doing research using two independent and dependent variables. The effect of manipulating independent variables in relation to dependent variables could be measured. This was for the purpose of establishing conditions and drawing conclusions. In this study, the researcher experimented on the powdered taro root, turmeric, and lemongrass included as ingredients of pasta in three different proportions, namely: 25%, 50%, and 75%.

Participants

The respondents for the research were selected using a purposive sampling method. Purposive sampling involves choosing individuals who meet the specific criteria relevant to the research objectives. The selection was targeted towards individuals with a direct connection to the pasta industry, specifically in Barangay Tumana, Marikina City. The research gathered the data from three distinct groups: 30 pasta lovers, 30 pasta sellers, and 30 pasta makers. These individuals were identified and chosen to serve as evaluators of the prepared pasta product.

Instruments

A survey questionnaire was prepared by the researcher, checked by her adviser and validated by experts. This was used to determine the acceptability and marketability level of the produced COCUCYNNE Fettuccine Pasta at 25%, 50%, and 75% proportions.

Ethical Considerations

The study made sure that protecting the respondents' anonymity and privacy is a top priority. Additionally, the proper consent and authorization will be considered. Participants in the study won't suffer any material, emotional, or physical harm from the researcher, and any information gathered from them will be acknowledged and presented fairly.

Results and Discussion

Produced COCUCYNNE Fettuccine Pasta Using Taro Root, Turmeric, and Lemongrass Powder as Additional Ingredients in Three Different Proportions of 25%, 50%, and 75% For 45mL Proportion

The powdered taro root, turmeric, lemon grass, and other ingredients were meticulously measured and blended in accordance with three distinct proportions: 25%, 50%, and 75%. Subsequently, these ingredients measured in three different proportions were combined and kneaded until a harmonious and smooth dough-like consistency was reached. The resulting dough was then thinly flattened and passed through a pasta cutter. Following this preparation, the COCUCYNNE Fettuccine Pasta was cooked in a pot of salted boiling water for precisely 5 minutes. The desired outcome was pasta that is cooked to perfection, maintaining an 'al dente' texture or firmness to the bite.

Physicochemical Analysis of COCUCYNNE Fettuccine Pasta in terms of Iron, Carbohydrates, pH level, and Moisture content

Analyte per 100 grams	Result
Iron	4.07 mg/100
Carbohydrates	65.7 g.
pH (10% Dispersion)	<u>6.05@22.6°C</u>
Moisture	14.6 g.

The composition of COCUCYNNE Fettuccine Pasta, as revealed in Table 8, carries significant implications for pasta lovers, sellers, and makers alike. The iron content of 4.07 mg/100 g signifies a nutritious choice, providing a source of this essential mineral in a

commonly enjoyed food. The substantial carbohydrate content of 65.7 g per 100 g also positions COCUCYNNE Fettuccine pasta as an energy-rich option, appealing to those seeking a satisfying and fueling meal. The pH level of 6.05 at 22.6°C and the moisture contents of 14.6 g contribute to the pasta's sensory characteristics, potentially enhancing its taste and texture.

Level of Acceptability of the Produced COCUCYNNE Fettuccine Pasta with Three Different Proportions of Taro Root, Turmeric, and Lemongrass Powder

For 25% Proportion

Table 2. Respondents' Evaluation on the Acceptability Level of COCUCYNNE Fettuccine Pasta with 25% Proportion of Taro Root, Turmeric and Lemongrass Powder as Regards Appearance

Indicators	Respondents					
	Pasta Lovers		Pasta Sellers		Pasta Makers	
	WM	VI	WM	VI	WM	VI
1. The COCUCYNNE Fettuccine Pasta looks delectable.	8.43	VAL	7.47	MAL	8.70	EAL
2. The COCUCYNNE Fettuccine Pasta has a distinctive greenish color.	8.43	VAL	7.47	MAL	8.70	EAL
3. The ingredients of COCUCYNNE Fettuccine Pasta are evenly distributed on the pasta strands.	8.43	VAL	7.47	MAL	8.70	EAL
4. The strands of COCUCYNNE Fettuccine Pasta are uniformly cut.	8.43	VAL	7.47	MAL	8.70	EAL
5. The COCUCYNNE Fettuccine Pasta has a presentable flat and long appearance like fettuccine.	8.43	VAL	7.47	MAL	8.70	EAL
Overall Weighted Means	8.43	VAL	7.47	MAL	8.70	EAL

It can be viewed from the table that the three groups of respondents evaluated the COCUCYNNE Fettuccine Pasta with 25% of taro root, turmeric, and lemongrass powder in terms of appearance as Very Acceptable Level (VAL) with overall weighted mean ratings of 8.43 for pasta lovers, 7.47 for pasta sellers, verbally interpreted as Moderately Acceptable Level (MAL), and 8.70 for pasta makers as Extremely Acceptable Level (EAL). This result that the produced product is accepted positively by the three groups of respondents. The result further shows that the three groups of respondents were satisfied with the appearance of the product.

Table 3. Respondents' Evaluation on the Acceptability Level of COCUCYNNE Fettuccine Pasta with 25% Proportion of Taro Root, Turmeric and Lemongrass Powder as Regards Aroma

Indicators	Respondents					
	Pasta Lovers		Pasta Sellers		Pasta Makers	
	WM	VI	WM	VI	WM	VI
1. The COCUCYNNE Fettuccine Pasta diffuses the slight but distinct lemon grass scent even after being cooked.	7.73	VAL	7.17	MAL	8.20	VAL
2. The light scent of lemon grass whets the appetite.	7.90	VAL	6.93	MAL	8.27	VAL
3. The COCUCYNNE Fettuccine Pasta has the pleasant smell of vegetable.	8.13	VAL	7.40	MAL	8.50	EAL
4. The smell of COCUCYNNE Fettuccine Pasta is similar to fresh vegetables.	8.13	VAL	7.50	VAL	8.63	EAL
5. The COCUCYNNE Fettuccine Pasta has a desirable smell.	7.97	VAL	7.30	MAL	8.53	EAL
Overall Weighted Means	7.97	VAL	7.26	MAL	8.43	VAL

It can be observed in the table that the pasta lovers and pasta maker respondents have equal evaluation on the acceptability of COCUCYNNE Fettuccine Pasta with 25% of taro root, turmeric, and lemongrass powder in terms of aroma with overall weighted mean ratings of 7.97 and 8.43, respectively, verbally interpreted as Very Acceptable Level (VAL) while pasta sellers evaluated it as Moderately Acceptable Level (MAL) with weighted mean rating of 7.26.

Table 4. Respondents' Evaluation on the Acceptability Level of COCUCYNNE Fettuccine Pasta with 25% Proportion of Taro Root, Turmeric and Lemongrass Powder as Regards Taste

Indicators	Respondents					
	Pasta Lovers		Pasta Sellers		Pasta Makers	
	WM	VI	WM	VI	WM	VI
1. The COCUCYNNE Fettuccine Pasta taste delicious.	8.30	VAL	7.23	MAL	8.60	EAL
2. The slight sweetness of taro root, light tang of turmeric, and mild herby taste of lemon grass are balanced in the pasta.	7.90	VAL	7.30	MAL	8.20	VAL
3. The COCUCYNNE Fettuccine Pasta is palatable	8.13	VAL	7.80	VAL	8.40	VAL
4. The taste of taro root, turmeric, and lemon grass complement each other.	8.00	VAL	7.33	MAL	8.43	VAL
5. The COCUCYNNE Fettuccine Pasta has a neutral flavor from the ingredients.	8.40	VAL	7.60	VAL	8.53	EAL
Overall Weighted Means	8.15	VAL	7.45	MAL	8.43	VAL

As gleaned in the table, both the pasta lovers and the pasta maker respondents rated the chips with COCUCYNNE Fettuccine Pasta with 25% of taro root, turmeric, and lemongrass as Very Acceptable Level (VAL) with overall weighted mean ratings of 8.15 and 8.43, respectively. On the other hand, despite the use of various ingredients the product’s neutral taste the pasta seller respondents rated it as Moderately Acceptable Level (MAL) with overall weighted mean rating of 7.45. This shows that the 25% proportion is well accepted by all the respondents. The data also show that the pasta makers rated the first and last indicators as Extremely Acceptable Level (EAL), this finding which implies that the produced product has a delicious taste and has a neutral flavor from the ingredients.

Table 5. Respondents’ Evaluation on the Acceptability Level of COCUCYNNE Fettuccine Pasta with 25% Proportion of Taro Root, Turmeric and Lemongrass Powder as Regards Texture

Indicators	Respondents					
	Pasta Lovers		Pasta Sellers		Pasta Makers	
	WM	VI	WM	VI	WM	VI
1. The COCUCYNNE Fettuccine Pasta is firm and slightly chewy.	8.00	VAL	7.40	MAL	8.53	EAL
2. The COCUCYNNE Fettuccine Pasta have an acceptable elastic texture.	8.23	VAL	7.43	MAL	8.70	EAL
3. The COCUCYNNE Fettuccine Pasta has a fine Texture.	8.37	VAL	7.63	VAL	8.77	EAL
4. The COCUCYNNE Fettuccine Pasta has a stringy Texture.	8.03	VAL	7.27	MAL	8.53	EAL
5. The COCUCYNNE Fettuccine Pasta remained al dente even after cooking.	8.10	VAL	7.43	MAL	8.60	EAL
Overall Weighted Means	8.15	VAL	7.43	MAL	8.63	EAL

The table shows the result of the evaluation of the pasta lover respondents on the COCUCYNNE Fettuccine Pasta with 25% of taro root, turmeric, and lemongrass powder in terms of texture as Very Acceptable Level with overall weighted mean ratings of 8.15, this implies that the produced product is likely has same texture from one of the markets. On the other hand, the evaluation of pasta sellers is 7.43 as verbally interpreted as Moderately Acceptable Level which indicated that the pasta elasticity needs improvement and 8.63 for pasta makers as Extremely Acceptable Level for its interesting texture that’s look like the regular pasta but with its slightly different shine and smoothness.

For 50% Proportion

Table 6. Respondents’ Evaluations on the Acceptability Level of COCUCYNNE Fettuccine Pasta with 50% Proportion of Taro Root, Turmeric and Lemongrass Powder as Regards Appearance

Indicators	Respondents					
	Pasta Lovers		Pasta Sellers		Pasta Makers	
	WM	VI	WM	VI	WM	VI
1. The COCUCYNNE Fettuccine Pasta looks delectable.	8.13	VAL	7.80	VAL	8.50	EAL
2. The COCUCYNNE Fettuccine Pasta has a distinctive greenish color.	7.90	VAL	7.43	MAL	8.43	VAL
3. The ingredients of COCUCYNNE Pasta are evenly distributed on the pasta strands.	8.47	VAL	7.80	VAL	8.70	EAL
4. The strands of COCUCYNNE Fettuccine Pasta are uniformly cut.	8.73	EAL	8.13	VAL	8.67	EAL
5. The COCUCYNNE Fettuccine Pasta has a presentable flat and long appearance like fettuccine.	8.53	EAL	8.13	VAL	8.77	EAL
Overall Weighted Means	8.35	VAL	7.86	VAL	8.61	EAL

It can be construed from the table that both the pasta lovers and the pasta seller-respondents evaluated the COCUCYNNE Fettuccine Pasta with 50% proportion of taro root, turmeric, and lemongrass powder in terms of appearance as Very Acceptable Level as evidenced by the overall weighted mean ratings of 8.35 and 7.86. Meanwhile the pasta makers evaluated it as Extremely Acceptable Level with an overall weighted mean rating of 8.61. This implies that the product produced has uniform cut, presentable flat, and has a long appearance like fettuccine.

Table 7. Respondents’ Evaluations on the Acceptability Level of COCUCYNNE Fettuccine Pasta with 50% Proportion of Taro Root, Turmeric and Lemongrass Powder as Regards Aroma

Indicators	Respondents					
	Pasta Lovers		Pasta Sellers		Pasta Makers	
	WM	VI	WM	VI	WM	VI
1. The COCUCYNNE Fettuccine Pasta diffuses the slight but distinct lemon grass scent even after being cooked.	7.83	VAL	7.27	MAL	8.10	VAL
2. The light scent of lemon grass whets the appetite.	8.07	VAL	7.13	MAL	8.37	VAL
3. The COCUCYNNE Fettuccine Pasta a pleasant smell of vegetables.	8.07	VAL	7.50	VAL	8.30	VAL
4. The smell of COCUCYNNE Fettuccine Pasta is similar to fresh vegetables.	8.37	VAL	7.60	VAL	8.43	VAL
5. The COCUCYNNE Fettuccine Pasta has a desirable smell.	8.03	VAL	7.60	VAL	8.40	VAL
Overall Weighted Means	8.07	VAL	7.42	MAL	8.32	VAL

As shown in the table, the respondents, namely: pasta lovers and pasta makers evaluated the COCUCYNNE Fettuccine Pasta with 50% of taro root, turmeric, and lemongrass in terms of aroma as Very Acceptable Level (VAL) with overall weighted mean ratings of 8.07 and 8.32. On the other hand, the pasta sellers evaluated the produced product with an overall weighted mean rating of 7.42 verbally interpreted as Moderately Acceptable Level (MAL) which implies that there is a need to improve the aroma of the pasta. It can be said that COCUCYNNE Fettuccine Pasta has a similar smell with and desirable freshly cooked vegetables.

Table 8. Respondents' Evaluations on the Acceptability Level of COCUCYNNE Fettuccine Pasta with 50% Proportion of Taro Root, Turmeric and Lemongrass Powder as Regards Taste

Indicators	Respondents					
	Pasta Lovers		Pasta Sellers		Pasta Makers	
	WM	VI	WM	VI	WM	VI
1. The COCUCYNNE Fettuccine Pasta taste delicious.	8.33	VAL	7.60	VAL	8.47	VAL
2. The slight sweetness of taro root, light tang of turmeric, and mild herby taste of lemon grass is balanced in the pasta.	7.93	VAL	7.63	VAL	8.17	VAL
3. The COCUCYNNE Fettuccine Pasta is Palatable.	8.20	VAL	8.10	VAL	8.40	VAL
4. The taste of taro root, turmeric, and lemon grass complement each other.	8.17	VAL	7.80	VAL	8.30	VAL
5. The COCUCYNNE Fettuccine Pasta has a neutral flavor from the ingredients.	8.47	VAL	7.90	VAL	8.50	EAL
Overall Weighted Means	8.22	VAL	7.81	VAL	8.37	VAL

It can be gleaned in the table that the pasta lovers, pasta sellers, and pasta makers respondents evaluated the acceptability of the COCUCYNNE Fettuccine Pasta with 50% of taro root, turmeric, and lemongrass powder in terms of appearance as Very Acceptable Level (VAL) with overall weighted mean ratings of 8.22, 7.81, and 8.37, respectively. It only implies that the product is accepted positively by all the respondents.

Table 9. Respondents' Evaluations on the Acceptability Level of COCUCYNNE Fettuccine Pasta with 50% Proportion of Taro Root, Turmeric and Lemongrass Powder as Regards Texture

Indicators	Respondents					
	Pasta Lovers		Pasta Sellers		Pasta Makers	
	WM	VI	WM	VI	WM	VI
1. The COCUCYNNE Fettuccine Pasta is firm and slightly chewy.	7.90	VAL	7.47	MAL	8.27	VAL
2. The COCUCYNNE Fettuccine Pasta have an acceptable elastic texture.	7.90	VAL	7.50	VAL	8.13	VAL
3. The COCUCYNNE Fettuccine Pasta has a fine Texture.	8.17	VAL	7.53	VAL	8.40	VAL
4. The COCUCYNNE Fettuccine Pasta has a stringy Texture.	7.97	VAL	7.33	MAL	8.23	VAL
5. The COCUCYNNE Fettuccine Pasta remained al dente even after cooking.	8.23	VAL	7.57	VAL	8.57	EAL
Overall Weighted Means	8.03	VAL	7.48	MAL	8.32	VAL

As presented in the table, the pasta lovers and pasta makers respondents rated the acceptability of the produced product in terms of texture as evidently shown on the overall weighted mean ratings of 8.03 for pasta lovers and 8.32 for pasta makers verbally interpreted as Very Acceptable Level (VAL) while the pasta seller-respondents rated it as Moderately Acceptable Level (MAL) with a weighted mean rating of 7.48. The findings possibly mean that the three groups of respondents consider the texture of the product as very acceptable.

For 75% Proportion

Table 10. Respondents' Evaluation on the Acceptability Level of COCUCYNNE Fettuccine Pasta with 75% Proportion of Taro Root, Turmeric and Lemongrass Powder as Regards Appearance

Indicators	Respondents					
	Pasta Lovers		Pasta Sellers		Pasta Makers	
	WM	VI	WM	VI	WM	VI
1. The COCUCYNNE Fettuccine Pasta looks delectable.	7.90	VAL	7.67	VAL	7.97	VAL
2. The COCUCYNNE Fettuccine Pasta have a distinctive greenish color.	7.97	VAL	7.53	VAL	8.30	VAL
3. The ingredients of COCUCYNNE Fettuccine Pasta are evenly distributed on the pasta strands.	8.47	VAL	7.83	VAL	8.47	VAL
4. The strands of COCUCYNNE Fettuccine Pasta are uniformly cut.	8.53	EAL	7.87	VAL	8.43	VAL
5. The COCUCYNNE Fettuccine Pasta has a presentable flat and long appearance like fettuccine.	8.40	VAL	8.17	VAL	8.33	VAL
Overall Weighted Means	8.25	VAL	7.81	VAL	8.30	VAL

It can be gleaned in the table that the pasta lovers, pasta sellers, and pasta makers' respondents evaluated the acceptability of the COCUCYNNE Fettuccine pasta with 75% of taro root, turmeric, and lemongrass powder in terms of appearance as Very Acceptable

Level (VAL) with overall weighted mean ratings of 8.25, 7.81, and 8.30, respectively.

Table 11. Respondents' Evaluation on the Acceptability Level of COCUCYNNE Fettuccine Pasta with 75% Proportion of Taro Root, Turmeric and Lemongrass Powder as Regards Aroma

Indicators	Respondents					
	Pasta Lovers		Pasta Sellers		Pasta Makers	
	WM	VI	WM	VI	WM	VI
1. The COCUCYNNE Fettuccine Pasta diffuses the slight but distinct lemon grass scent even after being cooked.	8.03	VAL	7.73	VAL	8.17	VAL
2. The light scent of lemon grass whets the appetite.	8.17	VAL	7.57	VAL	8.17	VAL
3. The COCUCYNNE Fettuccine Pasta has a pleasant smell of vegetables.	8.17	VAL	7.97	VAL	8.33	VAL
4. The smell of COCUCYNNE Fettuccine Pasta is similar to freshly cooked vegetables.	8.20	VAL	7.97	VAL	8.30	VAL
5. The COCUCYNNE Fettuccine Pasta has a desirable smell.	8.20	VAL	7.97	VAL	8.27	VAL
Overall Weighted Means	8.15	VAL	7.84	VAL	8.25	VAL

The table shows that the three groups of respondents evaluated the COCUCYNNE Fettuccine pasta with 75% of taro root, turmeric, and lemongrass powder in terms of taste as Very Acceptable Level (VAL) with overall weighted mean ratings of 8.15 for pasta lovers, 7.84 for pasta sellers, and 8.25 for pasta makers respondents. This implies that the product is positively accepted by all the respondents as regards aroma.

Table 12. Respondents' Evaluation on the Acceptability Level of COCUCYNNE Fettuccine Pasta with 75% Proportion of Taro Root, Turmeric and Lemongrass Powder as Regards Taste

Indicators	Respondents					
	Pasta Lovers		Pasta Sellers		Pasta Makers	
	WM	VI	WM	VI	WM	VI
1. The COCUCYNNE Fettuccine Pasta tastes delicious.	7.57	VAL	7.57	VAL	7.87	VAL
2. The slight sweetness of taro root, light tang of turmeric, and mild herby taste of lemon grass are balanced in the pasta.	7.67	VAL	7.67	VAL	8.00	VAL
3. The COCUCYNNE Fettuccine Pasta is palatable.	8.00	VAL	8.10	VAL	8.10	VAL
4. The taste of taro root, turmeric, and lemon grass complements each other.	7.70	VAL	7.87	VAL	8.13	VAL
5. The COCUCYNNE Fettuccine Pasta has a neutral flavor of the ingredients.	7.97	VAL	8.07	VAL	8.13	VAL
Overall Weighted Means	7.78	VAL	7.85	VAL	8.05	VAL

In a more detailed observation in the table, all the respondents namely pasta lovers, pasta sellers, and pasta makers rated the COCUCYNNE Fettuccine Pasta with 75% of taro root, turmeric, and lemongrass as Very Acceptable Level (VAL) with overall weighted mean ratings of 7.78, 7.85, and 8.05, respectively. This shows that the 75% proportion is well accepted by all the respondents.

Table 13. Respondents' Evaluation on the Acceptability Level of COCUCYNNE Fettuccine Pasta with 75% Proportion of Taro Root, Turmeric and Lemongrass Powder as Regards Texture

Indicators	Respondents					
	Pasta Lovers		Pasta Sellers		Pasta Makers	
	WM	VI	WM	VI	WM	VI
1. The COCUCYNNE Fettuccine Pasta is firm and slightly chewy.	7.53	VAL	7.03	MAL	7.77	VAL
2. The COCUCYNNE Fettuccine Pasta has an acceptable elastic texture.	7.63	VAL	7.23	MAL	7.70	VAL
3. The COCUCYNNE Fettuccine Pasta has a fine Texture.	7.87	VAL	7.47	MAL	7.87	VAL
4. The COCUCYNNE Fettuccine Pasta has a stringy Texture.	7.70	VAL	7.23	MAL	7.90	VAL
5. The COCUCYNNE Fettuccine Pasta remained al dente even after cooking.	8.00	VAL	7.40	MAL	8.13	VAL
Overall Weighted Means	7.75	VAL	7.27	MAL	7.87	VAL

The table shows that both the pasta lovers and pasta maker respondents have the same level of evaluation on the acceptability of taro root, turmeric, and lemongrass powder as ingredients in making COCUCYNNE Fettuccine Pasta with 75% proportion in terms of texture as evidenced by the weighted mean ratings of 7.75 and 7.87, both verbally interpreted as Very Acceptable Level (VAL). Meanwhile, the pasta seller respondents rated it as 7.27, verbally interpreted as Moderately Acceptable Level (MAL). It can be inferred that the pasta sellers' respondents like the COCUCYNNE with 75% proportion.

Significant Differences in the Evaluations of the Three Groups of Respondents of the Level of Acceptability of the Produced COCUCYNNE Fettuccine Pasta with 25%, 50%, and 75% Proportions of Taro Root, Turmeric, and Lemongrass

It is evident from the table that the evaluations of the pasta lovers, pasta sellers, pasta maker respondents on the acceptability level of the produced COCUCYNNE Fettuccine Pasta in 25% proportion as to appearance, aroma, taste and texture indicate significant

differences with the corresponding computed F values which are higher than the critical F value of 3.10. So, the evaluations provided by the respondents are alike.

Table 14. Summary of Analysis of Variance of the Respondents' Evaluation on the Acceptability Level of the Produced COCUCYNNE Fettuccine Pasta with 25% Proportion

Criteria	Computed F Value	Critical F Value	Decision	Interpretation
a. Appearance	15.90	3.10	Reject the H ₀	Significant
b. Aroma	13.10	3.10	Reject the H ₀	Significant
c. Taste	8.78	3.10	Reject the H ₀	Significant
d. Texture	12.32	3.10	Reject the H ₀	Significant

Table 15. Summary of Analysis of Variance of the Respondents' Evaluation on the Acceptability Level of the Produced COCUCYNNE Fettuccine Pasta with 50% Proportion

Criteria	Computed F Value	Critical F Value	Decision	Interpretation
a. Appearance	10.55	3.10	Reject the H ₀	Significant
b. Aroma	9.32	3.10	Reject the H ₀	Significant
c. Taste	4.26	3.10	Reject the H ₀	Significant
d. Texture	6.23	3.10	Reject the H ₀	Significant

The table exhibited that the evaluations of the pasta lovers, pasta sellers, and pasta maker respondents on the acceptability level of the produced COCUCYNNE Fettuccine Pasta in 50% proportion as to appearance, aroma, taste and texture show significant differences with the particular computed F values which are greater than the critical F value. This shows that the evaluations of the respondents are identical.

Table 16. Summary of Analysis of Variance of the Respondents' Evaluation on the Acceptability Level of the Produced COCUCYNNE Fettuccine Pasta with 75% Proportion

Criteria	Computed F Value	Critical F Value	Decision	Interpretation
a. Appearance	4.05	3.10	Reject the H ₀	Significant
b. Aroma	2.41	3.10	Reject the H ₀	Significant
c. Taste	0.63	3.10	Reject the H ₀	Significant
d. Texture	2.52	3.10	Reject the H ₀	Significant

It can be seen from the table that the evaluations of the pasta lovers, pasta sellers, pasta maker respondents on the acceptability level of the produced COCUCYNNE Fettuccine Pasta in 75% proportion as to aroma, taste and texture do not exhibit significant differences with the respective computed F values which are below the critical F value. Thus, the evaluations given by the respondents are the same, except for appearance.

Level of Marketability of the Produced COCUCYNNE Fettuccine Pasta in Three Different Proportions of Taro Root, Turmeric, and Lemongrass Powder

For 25% Proportion

Table 17. Respondents' Evaluation on the Marketability Level of the Produced COCUCYNNE Fettuccine Pasta in 25% Proportion of Taro Root, Turmeric, and Lemongrass Powder as to Supply Availability

Indicators	Respondents					
	Pasta Lovers		Pasta Sellers		Pasta Makers	
	WM	VI	WM	VI	WM	VI
1. The raw materials to be used in the COCUCYNNE Fettuccine Pasta are available locally and all year round.	4.87	VHL	4.73	VHL	4.90	VHL
2. The raw ingredients used in making COCUCYNNE Fettuccine Pasta can be grown in any type of weather and on any type of land.	4.70	VHL	4.63	VHL	4.83	VHL
3. The COCUCYNNE Fettuccine Pasta can be produced easily and cost less.	4.87	VHL	4.73	VHL	4.87	VHL
Overall Weighted Means	4.81	VHL	4.70	VHL	4.87	VHL

It can be observed in the table that the pasta lovers, pasta sellers, and pasta makers respondents evaluated the level of marketability of COCUCYNNE Fettuccine Pasta in terms of supply availability with the overall weighted mean ratings of 4.81, 4.70, and 4.87, respectively, as Very High Level. This could indicate the product's easy manufacturing due to the year-round availability of its ingredients.

It can be gleaned in the table that all the respondents, namely: pasta lovers, pasta sellers, and pasta makers evaluated the level of marketability of COCUCYNNE Fettuccine Pasta in terms of production cost with the overall weighted mean ratings of 4.69, 4.62, and 4.84, respectively which is verbally interpreted as Very High Level. This could indicate that because the product is reasonably priced, it will sell well once it is available in the market.

Table 18. Respondents' Evaluation on the Marketability Level of the Produced COCUCYNNE Fettuccine Pasta in 25% Proportion of Taro Root, Turmeric, and Lemongrass Powder as to Production Cost

Indicators	Respondents					
	Pasta Lovers		Pasta Sellers		Pasta Makers	
	WM	VI	WM	VI	WM	VI
1. The product could be consumed by people of all ages.	4.63	VHP	4.63	VHP	4.87	VHP
2. The product can satisfy consumers because of its nutritive value.	4.77	VHP	4.60	VHP	4.90	VHP
3. It can compete with other pasta with vegetables that are available in the market.	4.67	VHP	4.63	VHP	4.77	VHP
Overall Weighted Means	4.69	VHP	4.62	VHP	4.84	VHP

Table 19. Respondents' Evaluation on the Marketability Level of the Produced COCUCYNNE Fettuccine Pasta in 25% Proportion of Taro Root, Turmeric, and Lemongrass Powder as to Consumers Demand

Indicators	Respondents					
	Pasta Lovers		Pasta Sellers		Pasta Makers	
	WM	VI	WM	VI	WM	VI
1. The COCUCYNNE Fettuccine Pasta is affordable.	4.80	VHL	4.70	VHL	4.97	VHL
2. The raw materials are abundant which can reduce production costs.	4.93	VHL	4.73	VHL	4.97	VHL
3. The COCUCYNNE Fettuccine Pasta is cost-effective and cost-efficient.	4.73	VHL	4.67	VHL	4.90	VHL
Overall Weighted Means	4.82	VHL	4.70	VHL	4.94	VHL

It can be seen in the table that the three groups of respondents evaluated the product in terms of its consumer demand as Very High Level with overall weighted mean ratings of 4.82, 4.70, and 4.94, respectively. According to the data collected, every proportion may both compete with other pasta options on the market and benefit customers in terms of health.

For 50% Proportion

Table 20. Respondents' Evaluation on the Marketability Level of the Produced COCUCYNNE Fettuccine Pasta in 50% Proportion of Taro Root, Turmeric, and Lemongrass Powder as to Supply Availability

Indicators	Respondents					
	Pasta Lovers		Pasta Sellers		Pasta Makers	
	WM	VI	WM	VI	WM	VI
1. The raw materials to be used in the COCUCYNNE Fettuccine Pasta are available locally and all year round.	4.80	VHL	4.67	VHL	4.90	VHL
2. The raw ingredients used in making COCUCYNNE Fettuccine Pasta can be grown in any type of weather and on any type of land.	4.70	VHL	4.60	VHL	4.90	VHL
3. The COCUCYNNE Fettuccine Pasta can be produced easily and cost less.	4.83	VHL	4.77	VHL	4.77	VHL
Overall Weighted Means	4.78	VHL	4.68	VHL	4.86	VHL

As shown in the table the pasta lovers, pasta sellers, and pasta makers rated the COCUCYNNE Fettuccine Pasta supply availability as Very High Level as evidenced by overall weighted mean ratings of 4.78, 4.68, and 4.86, respectively. This could imply that once the product is available on the market, sales will be straightforward.

Table 21. Respondents' Evaluation on the Marketability Level of the Produced COCUCYNNE Fettuccine Pasta in 50% Proportion of Taro Root, Turmeric, and Lemongrass Powder as to Production Cost

Indicators	Respondents					
	Pasta Lovers		Pasta Sellers		Pasta Makers	
	WM	VI	WM	VI	WM	VI
1. The product could be consumed by people of all ages.	4.67	VHL	4.60	VHL	4.77	VHL
2. The product can satisfy consumers because of its nutritive value.	4.77	VHL	4.63	VHL	4.97	VHL
3. It can compete with other pasta with vegetables that are available in the market.	4.63	VHL	4.63	VHL	4.77	VHL
Overall Weighted Means	4.69	VHL	4.62	VHL	4.83	VHL

The table shows that in terms of production cost, the pasta lovers, pasta sellers, and pasta makers respondents rated the COCUCYNNE Fettuccine pasta with grand weighted mean ratings of 4.69, 4.62, and 4.83, respectively, verbally interpreted as Very High Level. It is evident that every respondent genuinely enjoys the COCUCYNNE Fettuccine Pasta and readily embraces it as a more affordable option for pasta available in the market.

Table 22. Respondents' Evaluation on the Marketability Level of the Produced COCUCYNNE Fettuccine Pasta in 50% Proportion of Taro Root, Turmeric, and Lemongrass Powder as to Consumers Demand

Indicators	Respondents					
	Pasta Lovers		Pasta Sellers		Pasta Makers	
	WM	VI	WM	VI	WM	VI
1. The COCUCYNNE Fettuccine Pasta is affordable.	4.73	VHL	4.70	VHL	5.00	VHL
2. The raw materials are abundant which can reduce production costs.	4.93	VHL	4.80	VHL	4.97	VHL
3. The COCUCYNNE Fettuccine is cost-effective and cost-efficient.	4.70	VHL	4.67	VHL	4.93	VHL
Overall Weighted Means	4.79	VHL	4.72	VHL	4.97	VHL

The data show that the three groups of respondents rated the produced COCUCYNNE pasta as Very High Level in terms of consumer demand with overall weighted mean ratings of 4.79 for pasta lovers, 4.72 for pasta sellers, and 4.97 for pasta makers respondents. This may suggest that the product have satisfied the customer demand and may even have positive effects on the customers' health.

For 75% Proportion

Table 23. Respondents' Evaluation on the Marketability Level of the Produced COCUCYNNE Fettuccine Pasta in 75% Proportion of Taro Root, Turmeric, and Lemongrass Powder as to Supply Availability

Indicators	Respondents					
	Pasta Lovers		Pasta Sellers		Pasta Makers	
	WM	VI	WM	VI	WM	VI
1. The raw materials to be used in the COCUCYNNE Fettuccine Pasta are available locally and all year round.	4.80	VHL	4.67	VHL	4.93	VHL
2. The raw ingredients used in making COCUCYNNE Fettuccine Pasta can be grown in any type of weather and on any type of land.	4.70	VHL	4.60	VHL	4.87	VHL
3. The COCUCYNNE Fettuccine Pasta can be produced easily and cost less.	4.77	VHL	4.70	VHL	4.80	VHL
Overall Weighted Means	4.76	VHL	4.66	VHL	4.87	VHL

The table shows that in terms of supply availability, the pasta lovers, pasta sellers, and pasta makers respondents rated the COCUCYNNE Fettuccine Pasta as Very High Level as evidenced by the overall weighted mean ratings of 4.76, 4.66, and 4.87, respectively. Additionally, it can be assumed that the ingredients were readily available and could have satisfied the supply's need economically.

Table 24. Respondents' Evaluation on the Marketability Level of the Produced COCUCYNNE Fettuccine Pasta in 75% Proportion of Taro Root, Turmeric, and Lemongrass Powder as to Production Cost

Indicators	Respondents					
	Pasta Lovers		Pasta Sellers		Pasta Makers	
	WM	VI	WM	VI	WM	VI
1. The product could be consumed by people of all ages.	4.67	VHL	4.70	VHL	4.80	VHL
2. The product can satisfy consumers because of its nutritive value.	4.70	VHL	4.67	VHL	4.83	VHL
3. It can compete with other pasta with vegetables that are available in the market.	4.67	VHL	4.67	VHL	4.90	VHL
Overall Weighted Means	4.68	VHL	4.68	VHL	4.84	VHL

Based on the given data in the Table, the pasta lovers, pasta sellers, and pasta makers respondents obtained the overall weighted mean ratings of 4.68, 4.68, and 4.84, respectively verbally interpreted as Very High Level. Based on the data gathered, it can be observed that even if all the respondents have the same evaluation it can be still observed that the pasta makers respondents have the highest overall weighted mean among the other respondents. It only implies that COCUCYNNE Fettuccine Pasta has market potential in terms of its production cost.

Table 25. Respondents' Evaluation on the Marketability Level of the Produced COCUCYNNE Fettuccine Pasta in 75% Proportion of Taro Root, Turmeric, and Lemongrass Powder as to Consumers Demand

Indicators	Respondents					
	Pasta Lovers		Pasta Sellers		Pasta Makers	
	WM	VI	WM	VI	WM	VI
1. The COCUCYNNE Fettuccine Pasta is affordable.	4.70	VHL	4.73	VHL	4.97	VHL
2. The raw materials are abundant which can reduce production costs.	4.90	VHL	4.80	VHL	5.00	VHL
3. The COCUCYNNE Fettuccine Pasta is cost-effective and cost-efficient.	4.70	VHL	4.70	VHL	4.97	VHL
Overall Weighted Means	4.77	VHL	4.74	VHL	4.98	VHL

The data in the table shows, that all the three groups of respondents rated the produced COCUCYNNE Fettuccine Pasta as Very High Level as regards to consumers demand as evidenced by the overall weighted mean ratings of 4.77 for pasta lovers, 4.74 for pasta sellers, and 4.98 for pasta makers respondents. From the data gathered, it can be observed that the 75% proportion has a positive market potential in terms of consumers' demand since it has the highest overall weighted mean.

Significant Differences in the Evaluation of the Three Groups of Respondents on the Level of Marketability of the Produced COCUCYNNE Fettuccine Pasta

Table 26. Summary of Analysis of Variance of Respondents' Evaluations on the Marketability Level of the Produced COCUCYNNE Fettuccine Pasta in 25% Proportion

Criteria	Computed F Value	Critical F Value	Decision	Interpretation
a. Supply Availability	1.67	3.10	Fail to Reject the H ₀	Not Significant
b. Production Cost	2.00	3.10	Fail to Reject the H ₀	Not Significant
c. Consumer Demand	4.60	3.10	Reject the H ₀	Significant

The table reflects that the evaluations of the pasta lovers, pasta sellers, pasta maker respondents on the marketability level of the produced COCUCYNNE Fettuccine Pasta in 25% proportion in terms of supply availability and production cost do not indicate significant differences with the corresponding computed F values which are below the critical F value of 3.10. This suggests that the evaluations from respondents are consistent, except for differences related to consumer demand.

Table 27. Summary of Analysis of Variance of Respondents' Evaluations on the Marketability Level of the Produced COCUCYNNE Fettuccine Pasta in 50% Proportion

Criteria	Computed F Value	Critical F Value	Decision	Interpretation
a. Supply Availability	1.81	3.10	Fail to Reject the H ₀	Not Significant
b. Production Cost	1.77	3.10	Fail to Reject the H ₀	Not Significant
c. Consumer Demand	5.08	3.10	Reject the H ₀	Significant

As specified in the table, the evaluations of the pasta lovers, pasta sellers, pasta maker respondents on the marketability level of the produced COCUCYNNE pasta in 50% proportion in terms of supply availability and production cost do not imply significant differences with the respective computed F values which are less than the critical F value. Hence, the evaluations from the respondents are alike, with the exception of consumer demand.

Table 28. Summary of Analysis of Variance of Respondents' Evaluations on the Marketability Level of the Produced COCUCYNNE Fettuccine Pasta in 75% Proportion

Criteria	Computed F Value	Critical F Value	Decision	Interpretation
a. Supply Availability	2.15	3.10	Fail to Reject the H ₀	Not Significant
b. Production Cost	1.58	3.10	Fail to Reject the H ₀	Not Significant
c. Consumer Demand	5.30	3.10	Reject the H ₀	Significant

The table demonstrated that the evaluation of the pasta lovers, pasta sellers, pasta maker respondents on the marketability level of the produced COCUCYNNE Fettuccine Pasta in 75% proportion in terms of supply availability and production cost do not signify significant differences with the particular computed F values which are lower than the critical F value. This shows that the evaluations of the respondents are comparable, except for differences related to consumer demand.

Comments and Suggestions Offered by the Respondents to Improve the Produced Product

The respondents asserted that the produced COCUCYNNE Fettuccine pasta has a neutral taste which is good, since it can easily absorb the flavors of sauces and seasonings when paired to it. They also included how COCUCYNNE Fettuccine Pasta looks delicious and has reasonable price, which undoubtedly introduces a new trend to the market.

The respondents suggested that adding cornstarch and baking soda will improve the produced COCUCYNNE Fettuccine Pasta to make its texture more elastic when boiled. They also added that improving the color of the COCUCYNNE Fettuccine Pasta will make it more palatable by using natural coloring from dried pigmented plants.

Conclusions

Based on the findings of the study, the following conclusions were drawn:

1. The COCUCYNNE Fettuccine Pasta with 50% proportion is the most acceptable proportion in terms of appearance, aroma, color, taste, and texture as compared to the 25% proportion and 75% proportion.
2. The COCUCYNNE Fettuccine Pasta has great market level and has shown consistency across all proportions of the product produced.
3. The examination of the physicochemical characteristics of COCUCYNNE Fettuccine Pasta, showed several positive attributes. Firstly, it boasts a low iron content, ensuring that regular consumption will not lead to adverse health effects. Additionally, its

carbohydrate composition provides a significant energy boost. The slightly acidic pH level contributes to its freshness and reduces the risk of food spoilage and microbial growth, ensuring a longer shelf life. Fresh COCUCYNNE Fettuccine Pasta can be conveniently stored in the refrigerator, wrapped in plastic, for up to 2 days, while dried pasta can be safely stored in an airtight container in a cool, dry place, lasting for over three months without any noticeable changes, as long as it maintains its usual aroma.

4. The COCUCYNNE Fettuccine Pasta has a great marketability potential since it caters to health-conscious consumers seeking both taste and well-being.

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